

Deep-tech driven inclusive and socially-aware circular material joining & welding for a safe future

D6.1 Quality assurance plan

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A. Introduction

This document has been prepared for internal use for an efficient output development and open innovation and co-creation framework by Helixconnect Europe S.R.L, IMPACTSCI and the other WELDIFY project partners. It shall provide the project partners with the necessary details and tools to effectively undertake the internal and external quality management of the project throughout its duration, in particular this refers to the scope and objectives, methodology and tools for quality assurance of this project. Formative evaluation results will be used. It shall facilitate the recording of the results in each phase of the project.

The main aims and objectives of this document are:

- To identify and measure the project's performance (outputs) and progress of process
- To raise awareness about quality within the project and support decision making processes,
- To provide feedback, particularly improvement potentials related to processes and outputs to coordinator and project partners about these,
- To contribute to clear user orientation in the development of project outputs.

B. Aim and objectives of WELDIFY – overview

As manufacturing technology has continuously evolved over the years, there has been an ongoing need for enhancements in the manufacturing sector to address contemporary demands, especially for the automotive and construction industries. This includes producing components with high efficiency, maximum accuracy, and ease. Welding processes provide versatile capabilities that are applicable across a broad spectrum of industries. The unique signals generated during welding operations, such as fluctuations in welding current, temperature variations, and acoustic emissions, make these processes well-suited for digitization as they pose physical health risk for operators¹. On top of this, welding fumes pose a distinct occupational risk due to the intricate processes that lead to their formation, making it challenging to characterise these emissions². Furthermore, photobiological hazards from

¹ Kapil, Angshuman, S. Q. Moinuddin, and Abhay Sharma. "Digitization of welding processes." *Joining Processes for Dissimilar and Advanced Materials*. Woodhead Publishing, 2022. 483–512.

² E. Quecke, B. Quemerais, Z. Hashisho, Review of welding fume emission factor development, *Annals of Work Exposures and Health*, Volume 67, Issue 6, July 2023, Pages 675–693, <https://doi.org/10.1093/annweh/wxad024>

artificial optical radiation focuses on Shielded Metal Arc Welding (SMAW), a prevalent arc welding method that uses a hand-held system and finds widespread application in both occupational and domestic settings³. Recycling metals plays a crucial role in environmental sustainability and resource conservation across Europe⁴, a continent at the forefront of green initiatives. However, the utilisation of recycled metals, particularly in critical applications, demands rigorous quality control to avoid compromising safety and performance. Challenges associated with recycled metals, when not properly refined or tested, include diminished material properties such as strength, ductility, and corrosion resistance.

These deficiencies can precipitate failures in critical infrastructure and manufactured goods, leading to potentially catastrophic outcomes. In Europe, the construction sector has witnessed incidents where the integrity of materials, including those involving recycled metals, came under scrutiny. For instance, the partial collapse of a school roof in the Netherlands was attributed to structural failure, prompting investigations into material quality and construction practices. Although not always publicly attributed to recycled materials, such incidents underscore the importance of stringent standards for material selection, especially in load-bearing applications.

The automotive industry in Europe, renowned for its stringent safety and quality standards, is not immune to the challenges posed by recycled materials. Recycled metals used in car parts must undergo thorough testing to meet the high standards required for safety and performance. Failures⁵ in critical components such as brake lines, steering mechanisms, or structural frames due to substandard materials can have dire consequences. Statistical data⁶ on accidents specifically attributed to the use of recycled metals in Europe is sparse, as incidents are often reported and analysed under broader categories such as material failure, construction defects, or manufacturing flaws⁷. European Union regulations and standards, such as the Eurocodes for construction and automotive⁸, are designed to ensure the safety and reliability of all materials, including recycled ones, used in critical applications.

3 G.A. Gourzoulidis, C.A. Bouroussis, A. Achtipis, M. Kazasidis, D. Pantelis, A. Markoulis, I. Konstantakopoulos, F.V. Topalis, Photobiological hazards in shielded metal arc welding, *Physica Medica*, Volume 106, 2023, 102520, ISSN 1120-1797, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmp.2022.102520>

4 Sustainable recycling, use of secondary raw materials and Just Transition in the European ferrous and nonferrous metal industry CCM1/191-EESC-2022-01-01

5 Day, A. J., & Bryant, D. (2022). *Braking of road vehicles*. Butterworth-Heinemann.

6 Metal Recycling Factsheet - EuRIC AISBL - Recycling: Bridging Circular Economy & Climate Policy https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/sites/default/files/euric_metal_recycling_factsheet.pdf

7 Greuter, E., & Zima, S. (2012). *Engine failure analysis*. Sae International.

8 <https://eurocodes.jrc.ec.europa.eu/en-eurocodes/eurocodes-family>

These regulations mandate rigorous testing and certification processes that recycled materials must pass to be deemed safe for use. While the direct correlation between recycled metals and specific accidents might be underreported or difficult to isolate in statistical analyses, the potential for increased risk is acknowledged in the automotive and construction sectors. This awareness drives the ongoing improvement of recycling processes, quality control measures, and regulatory standards across Europe to safeguard against material-related failures. Through a combination of digital tools and a network for skilled labour, WELDIFY can help the automotive and construction industries more effectively manage their workforce needs. It can offer training programs or partnerships with educational institutions to upskill workers, making them more adept at using new technologies and methods, thus addressing the skilled labour gap. By focusing on sustainability, WELDIFY will help companies across these sectors meet stricter environmental regulations and consumer expectations for eco-friendly practices, it will involve providing platforms that facilitate the more efficient use of resources, reduce emissions, and promote recycling and circular economy principles.

WELDIFY underscores the critical importance of circular economy practices, automation, safety, inclusivity, and sustainability in addressing the industry's challenges, thus the consortium aims to develop and promote training materials that emphasise the use of recycled materials, safety protocols, and environmentally friendly practices in welding and material joining. Automation is another focal point of our proposal, as we acknowledge its potential to enhance efficiency and productivity in welding processes. To incorporate this into our training program, we plan to integrate advanced welding techniques with robotics and human-machine interaction, ensuring comprehensive training for participants. The project intends to raise safety standards by leveraging preventive and predictive optimization techniques within welding processes, ultimately reducing the risk of accidents, and improving overall safety measures⁹.

The proposals incorporation of advanced welding techniques and robotics aligns with potential automation-related priorities of the call. Given the current severe shortage of workers in the industry¹⁰, there is an urgent need for a solution to expedite the training process without compromising on the essential fundamentals. This is crucial because VET and HED learners must have a deep understanding of what works in various situations and why it works, rather than simply learning a set of isolated skills (e.g., pushing buttons and welding joints) and immediately starting work. The aim is for learners and professionals to follow established procedures while also comprehending the underlying reasons for the procedures' effectiveness. In response to

⁹<https://www.gz-supplies.com/news/the-future-of-welding-technology-advancements-trends-and-implications/>

¹⁰EURES Report on labour shortages and surpluses 2022. ISBN 978-92-9401-055-1 DOI 10.2883/67288 HP-AA-23-001-EN-C. <https://www.ela.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2023-03/eures-labour-shortages-report-2022.pdf>

this situation, augmented and virtual reality (AR/VR) are emerging as viable solutions, particularly for one of the most hands-on processes in manufacturing environments: welding¹¹. The development of a comprehensive training toolkit and a micro-credential system for welding courses supports the call's potential priorities related to education and skill development by contributing to the continuous development of digital skills, environmental awareness, job awareness and entrepreneurial abilities among participants. The proposal's emphasis on collaboration, access to diverse learners, and real-world industrial pilot courses aligns with the promotion of industry partnerships and continuous learning, which are priorities of the call.

General Objectives and their relevance:

GO1: Fostering new, innovative and multidisciplinary approaches to teaching and learning in the field of circular material welding (CMW) by develop an advanced digital welding toolkit for over 5000 learners, emphasising material resilience, quality and circular economy. Support learner employability via micro credentials under the EIT Deep Tech Talent Initiative label and stimulate a sense of initiative and entrepreneurial attitudes with regards to achieving resilient CMW solutions, mind-sets and skills in adult, vocational and higher education learners.

GO2: Co-create a trainer-friendly human-machine interaction toolkit to enhance safety and enable employment opportunities for individuals with disabilities, in line with WELDIFY's mission to transform welding processes and promote inclusivity. Support innovative teaching & learning methods – i.e. enabling trainers to use robotics for welding aligns with WELDIFY's aim to revolutionise welding processes, implemented hybrid teaching factories as work-based learning, relying on real time learner analytics.

GO3: Facilitating urgent need of co-creation on CMW knowledge among higher education, VET stakeholders, SMEs, and public sector to support inclusive upskilling and regional economic growth filling the gap of skilled workforce in the field of CMW (especially by providing access to education and employment of people with disabilities)

GO4: Build a cross-disciplinary platform for effective work-based learning, cooperation, and skill-gap monitoring. Establishing a comprehensive platform aligns with WELDIFY's aim to promote cooperation among various education and training sectors while providing a space for learners to apply welding practices in industrial settings. The platform will be linked with EIT's Deep Tech Talent Initiative (DTTI) platform in order to fast-track the upload of WELDIFY's courses on the DTTI and contribute to upskilling European VET learners on deep tech.

¹¹ \$105+ Mn Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) Market is Expected to Grow at a CAGR of over 35.7% During 2022-2028 | Vantage Market Research.

C. Aim & objectives of the quality assurance plan

The Quality Assurance Plan will describe in detail issues such as the following: 1) Actionable and effective guidance for achieving high-quality standards for all project's activities. 2) Detailed rules and procedures for online and offline dissemination actions in conformance with legal and ethical values. 3) Effective monitoring and control processes. 4) Models and templates for the project's deliverables and reports for easy and effective monitoring.

Each framework will establish the basic ground to be followed by all consortium members.

Objectives of the Quality Assurance

1. To ensure the project timescales and deliverables are realistic and are closely monitored and if necessary adjusted throughout the lifetime of the project
2. To monitor that the project runs to the proposed budget throughout the lifetime of the project
3. To monitor that the engagement with all project target groups is conducted to a high standard ensuring the necessary outcomes are achieved
4. To give advice and guidance to the project manager and the project team during the course of the project and encourage them to re-visit timescales, outcomes and outputs throughout the project
5. To produce an Exploitation and intellectual property agreement and strategy
6. To develop Quality standards for open innovation and co-creation framework

D. Overall quality assurance tasks

Quality assurance & evaluation: A quality plan will be developed to define specific quality performance indicators in each output of the project based on: (i) process and project management, (ii) partnership; (iii) results.

The quality plan will:

- define all the evaluation tools that will be used;
- describe clear evaluation criteria;
- create a shared understanding of the purposes, use, and users of the evaluation results;
- foster project's transparency to stakeholders and decision makers;
- facilitate evaluation capacity building among partners and stakeholders and also best evaluation practices.

The evaluation procedure will be based on:

- Analysis of project outputs and long-term outcomes (including the identification of improvements);
- Observations of interactions during implementation of all project activities;
- Surveys of personnel from partner organisations;
- Evaluation forms from participants in dissemination events and WELDIFY blended pilots;
- Assessment of the skill-gap mitigation of target groups (beginning vs end of the project) via competence grids;
- External peer review based on an External Quality Assurance Board (EQAB). The EQAB members (scientists, industrial & policy representatives) are internationally renowned, independent experts working in the areas covered by WELDIFY. The EQAB will review technical results of the project and give non-binding advice towards further advancements to be achieved. They will join WELDIFY project meetings once per year;
- External evaluation with mid term and final reports by an appointed External Evaluator (see WP6).

Monitoring and evaluation process: WELDIFY' quality processes will be led by IMPACTSCI, specifically by Ms Andreia Morgado (quality assurance manager – QAM) who has strong expertise in producing high quality Erasmus+ project results. He will chair a quality assurance committee (QAC) composed of members from each partner organisation.

The Quality Assurance Manager (from IMPACTSCI), Project Manager (from CERTH), the Steering Group, QAC & EQAB will have the task of ensuring monitoring and evaluation of the progress made towards objectives and results envisaged.

Quality control and evaluation points:

- Financial management:
 - formal reporting, every 6 months;
- Project implementation (timeline) quality check during the monthly calls;
- Deliverable/result/activity sign off timeline, to be submitted to quality control 2 months prior to sign off deadline to be subjected to internal peer review and 1 month before sign-off to external peer review (to the external advisory board). This applies to both formal results as well as to progress results (i.e. pilot methodologies, dissemination materials, etc all broken down per task define in each WP);
- Staff engagement and involvement levels, to be monitored every 6 months via surveys;
- Project meeting evaluation: right after their accomplishment using an online questionnaire developed by IMPACTSCI and focusing on 3 dimensions: before the meeting, during the meeting and after the meeting;

- Evaluation of dissemination events will be done using evaluation questionnaires (right after each event) developed by IMPACTSCI focusing on 3 dimensions: organisation, facilitators, personal experience;
- Evaluation of the platform pilots will be done using evaluation questionnaires (before & after each event) developed by IMPACTSCI focusing on 3 dimensions: organisation, facilitators, personal experience, interaction & engagement, ease of technology use, competence level (before and after);
- All the above will be integrated into Interim quality reports - every 6 months;
- External evaluation by an appointed evaluator (mid term and final).

All of the above quality checks will be built around SWOT analyses items: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats, both in a quantitative and qualitative assessment in order to enable a true improvement identification.

In order to successfully implement the vision of WELDIFY QAP, the kaizen methodology will be adopted and this will imply: teamwork, personal discipline, improved morale and engagement, quality circles, and constant suggestions for improvement. On top of this, quality assurance is deeply embedded in each WP and activity development via internal and external peer-review stages (as it can be seen in the WP development tasks).

A timeline of the quality assurance actions consists of:

- **Month 1** - QAP will be developed containing specific key performance indicators (KPIs) and guidelines for the project implementation and WP development Quality assurance monitoring spreadsheets also made available on the shared Google Drive File. A first meeting of the QAC will be organised.
- **Months 6,12,18,24,30,36** - semestrial quality assurance monitoring meetings/check-ups (cross-checking the indicators and identifying potential risks/improvement opportunities) at the QAC and EQAB intervention level. The QAC and EQAB will hold online meetings to facilitate the effective quality assurance process.
- **Months 6, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36** (during the formal project meetings), QAC meetings will also take place to formally report on quality standards and formally deploy/co-create corrective measures.
- **Months 6, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36**: formal quality assurance monitoring reports will be issued by IMPACTSCI.

Quality assurance monitoring will be done via a commonly shared spreadsheet. Every activity and sub-activity will have a sheet, which will be filled out by the responsible institution of the activity/sub-activity, providing information as start and end date, outcomes/outputs, indicators, or source of verification. Within each sheet, a link to the folder containing the output/activity

development will be provided. The organisation responsible for the activity will be asked to upload to this folder all the complementary documentation that supports the Outcomes/Outputs, especially those related to the Source of Verification. The indicators for measuring the quality and achievement of project activities consist of the following categories (IMPACTSCI will develop the evaluation tools which will be peer-reviews by the QAC and EQAB):

PROJECT MEETINGS: all project meetings will be evaluated right after their implementation using an online questionnaire developed by IMPACTSCI and focusing on 3 dimensions: before the meeting (preparations, agenda), during the meeting (effectiveness) and after the meeting (minutes, registers).

DISSEMINATION EVENTS: will be evaluated using evaluation questionnaires focusing on 3 dimensions: organisation, facilitation, personal experience.

VIRTUAL PILOTS: will be done using evaluation questionnaires focusing on 3 dimensions: organisation, facilitators, personal experience, interaction & engagement.

OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCE (OER): Degree of alignment to standards, Quality of explanation of the subject matter, Utility of materials designed to support teaching - Quality of assessment, Quality of technological interactivity, Quality of instructional and practice exercises, Assurance of accessibility, Content quality, Motivation, Presentation design - Usability, Accessibility, Educational value, Overall rating.

PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION: Timely implementation of tasks (minimum delay), Compliance with the rules of the funding program (no deviation), Continuous and transparent flow of information through the online depository (min. 90% of project documentation is shared through the Google drive).

SATISFACTION INDICATORS: positive feedback and satisfaction from the target groups with regards to the project outputs (85%), internal staff satisfaction from working on the project (85%).

The project quality assurance and evaluation activities (what, how, where) and division of work are presented in Annex 1 while the specific deliverables (outputs/outcomes) are presented in Annex 2.

E. Quality assurance indicators

The extent to which WELDIFY's results and objectives have been met will be measured against the following broad categories of indicators:

- measures concerning impact on the target groups
- measures of behavioural change
- measures of quality of the outputs that have been developed
- measures of the dissemination and exploitation capacity

QUALITY RISK MITIGATION MECHANISMS:

- Clear definition of roles of the QAC
- Engagement with EQAB
- 6-month quality checks
- Concrete indicators in the QAP at various levels (prototype/concept, interim draft and final draft)

A sample of the quality assurance and evaluation indicators can be found in Annex 3.

F. Quality assurance methodological approach

Firstly, in their relationships within the overall consortium, each project partner shall be committed to the following rules and requirements.

Being responsive

To contribute to the value and effectiveness of the Project, it is vital that Project Partners respond to messages, enquiries and requests quickly and comprehensively. The following principles must be implemented:

- A reasonable time limit will be enforced for acknowledging receipt of messages: inquiries should be responded to within 5 working days,
- Project Partners will always provide a response, no matter what the outcome,
- Necessary tools must be in place to immediately inform other Project Partners of staff absence or office closure which will affect the above response time limits and Network Partners must always provide an alternative contact or expected date of return,
- Regularly check all incoming information and perform any required actions to the deadlines requested,
- Inform Consortium Coordinator of any issues which could affect the proper functioning of the consortium.

Dealing with non-responsive partners:

- In the first instance, the partner will be e-mailed by the project coordinator to enquire as to any concerns that may be preventing them from completing tasks. If no reply:

- Follow up e-mail will be sent with a specific to-do list and deadlines attached. At this time, this partner will be encouraged to call the project leader with specific times given. If no reply:
- Follow up email stressing the urgency of getting in touch and the implication of further delays for the project. The coordinator shall call the partner. If no reply:
- Registered official letter 1 to the Partner and its Legal representative offering an opportunity to negotiate deadlines to support the non-responsive partner. If no reply:
- Registered official letter 2 to Partner and its Legal representative setting a formal deadline for the partner to communicate problems/ complete work. If no reply:
- Registered official letter 3 to the Partner and its Legal representative dissolving its participation in the partnership.

Behave professionally at all times, be cooperative and try to find synergies

To qualitatively guarantee the excellence of the project, project partners are required to be dedicated to providing a professional service to their colleagues within the consortia. To uphold the professionalism of the consortium, partners must:

- Respect mutually established deadlines and be accountable for agreed measures and rules of the consortia,
- Follow agreed consortium processes and procedures at all times,
- Make the consortia aware of areas of expertise, through consortia tools or otherwise, and be prepared to use this expertise when assistance is requested from another partner,
- Be realistic in the level of support they can offer a colleague and communicate any difficulties that arise in delivering this support,
- Endeavour to continuously update and improve the skills of individual staff members to help enhance the knowledge and expertise of the consortia overall.

Share important information within the consortium

A two-way flow of important information between consortium coordinator and project partners is vital to ensure successful communication. For its part, consortium coordinator is responsible for:

- The dissemination of all correspondence with regards to project related activities,
- The provision of sufficient notice of deadlines for actions relating to reporting or contractual issues.

Contributing to the spirit of the project consortium

Sharing a common vision, aims and values will enhance the commitment, enthusiasm and effectiveness of the consortium, as well as allowing partners to learn from one another and share good practices.

To maintain this project spirit, project partners should:

- Be supportive and cooperative with their project colleagues while striving to make trusting, sustainable relationships,
- Treat other as they would expect to be treated themselves,
- Ensure contact details, changes in personnel and areas of expertise are kept up to date via consortium tools which will allow any partner to find the most appropriate contact quickly and confidently.

Secondly, To ensure good quality of the project's work processes, activities and products, especially all Work packages, activities and deliverables in the frame of the project the 'PDCA' cycle will be implemented as continuous improvement process. It consists of the following four steps: "Plan → Do → Check → Act (PDCA)".

Plan: The "plan" means to establish the way to complete the projects' objectives and achieve project results according to the expected predictions. The first plan will be provided by work package lead partners; each partner will follow this plan to plan its implementation within their own organisation.

Do: Subsequently the following "do" step ensures that new processes among partners, coordinator and third parties (like stakeholders, target group etc.) are encouraging an implementation under controlled circumstances. They shall be committed to implement the foreseen plan in time and with the foreseen results.

Check: The "checking" process commences when partners' or third parties' activities, implementation, communication and key project processes are evaluated – which, in this project will be an on-going process. The results will be evaluated according to a joint methodology in order to identify changes and initiate modifications where necessary.

Act: The final stage of the cycle introduces measures to standardise procedures within the projects' development or make improvement to enhance these. This will be managed by answering to and applying recommendations found upon the above described evaluation within the step 'check'.

Through this cycle, project partners and coordinator are provided with the opportunity to observe, assess and refine all the projects processes and outcomes.

The quality assurance process will focus on the work packages and deliverables and will be performed according to the following procedure:

Internal Quality Evaluation (peer review system)

The internal quality evaluation is mainly based on the questionnaires (see the appendix) that cover standardised questions about the realisation of the project.

It enables to find out how the project's goals and activities are carried out (identification, completion with respect to timelines), assess the progress of the project (evaluation of progress so far), identify project problems if any (with internal and/or external communication, deadlines, financial, technical, organisation, administrative) with the ways/suggestions to overcome them, Capture significant details about activities and outputs/results of communication / open innovation and co creation and dissemination throughout the project lifestyle (one of the questions is devoted to open innovation and co-creation & dissemination activities). The internal quality evaluation will be made also during partners' meetings, online meetings, phone and e-mail contacts.

Evaluation questionnaires will contain questions enabling broader description and deeper assessment of different project deliverables/outputs as well as feedback/comments from stakeholders. The Bi-Yearly Monitoring/Evaluation Questionnaire Form will be completed by project partners' staff (managed by IMPACTSCI) .

The other evaluation questionnaires will be collected by all partners involved and sent to the partner responsible for specific deliverable to prepare cumulative assessment of the deliverable/IO.

The role of all Partners:

- giving information and data on the Project performance and Progress – feeding the Quality Assurance evaluation system,
- collecting info/feedback from stakeholders and end-users,
- contributing to and updating evaluations/reports,
- co-operating in early detection and solving of problems.

The role of IMPACTSCI :

- leading quality assurance and activities within,
- co-ordinating Partners' input,
- preparing evaluations/reports.
- All answers will be collected, analysed and use for evaluation reports.

G. Quality assurance best practices

Evaluation is a process which:

- a) Supports a project, by measuring the extent to which the objectives are met,
- b) Identifies achievements,
- c) Identifies areas for improvement,
- d) Encourages decisions to be taken, including changes to project objectives and/or methodologies.

Quality assurance is a component of quality management and it is focused on providing confidence that quality requirements will be fulfilled (ISO 9000).

Below it is given an overview of concepts and terms concerning quality assessment and evaluation based on best practices from the SUSTAIN-CE project (Erasmus+ KA2).

C O N C E P T S T E R M S	QUALITY	<p>Quality can be determined by comparing a set of inherent characteristics with a set of requirements. If those inherent characteristics meet all requirements, high or excellent quality is achieved. If those characteristics do not meet all requirements, a low or poor level of quality is achieved.</p> <p>Note: Quality is always relative to a set of requirements.</p>
	EVALUATION	<p>Systematic collection and analysis of information on the actual performance of a project. Its aim is to analyse the relevance, progress, success and cost-effectiveness of the project. An evaluation compares planned results with the actual results of a project. It is a diagnostic tool.</p>
	MONITORING	<p>Continuing management exercise. Its aim is to supervise the accounting and administrative processes of a project. When implementing a project, monitoring deals almost exclusively with the conversion of inputs into outputs. This exercise will help to evaluate if what was supposed to be done really is. Adjustments to the project are possible when monitoring is done throughout the project management life cycle.</p>
	PERFORMANCE MEASURES	<p>Indicators that provide information (either quantitative or qualitative) on the extent to which the results of a project have been achieved. Evaluation is often confused with measures used to evaluate. Any activity which aims at interpreting results, or data obtained from measures, are part of an evaluation. To assure that the evaluation process leads to good decision-making, it must rest on correct and precise measures.</p>
	EFFICIENCY	<p>Refers to producing planned outputs within budgetary limits and established deadlines.</p> <p>For example: Was the implementation of the project well managed?</p>
	EFFECTIVENESS	<p>Refers to achieving planned results and contributing to attain established goals and objectives.</p> <p>For example: To what extent were the project's objectives achieved?</p>
	IMPACT	<p>Refers to the intended or unintended, negative or positive, consequences of a project, some of which happen only sometime after the end of the project.</p> <p>For example: What were the consequences and the effects of the project for the target groups?</p>

GOALS	A general statement of desired outcomes to be achieved over a specified period of time (the reasons for which the National Agency wishes to undertake the project).
OBJECTIVES	The essential and long-term benefits towards which efforts are directed and for which outputs are to be produced.
OUTPUTS	Tangible products (including services and events) that are necessary to achieve the objectives of the project and delivered to the project's target groups and stakeholders. Outputs relate to the completion (rather than the conduct) of activities and are the type of results over which partners have a high degree of influence. They are also the specific results obtained from the management of inputs.
INPUTS	Activities and resources (human, material, financial) used to carry out activities, produce outputs and achieve results.
RESULTS	The consequences or changes directly attributed to the activities of the project. The results achieved may be measured with respect to the inputs, outputs, goals and objectives of the project.
PRODUCT QUALITY	The quality of a product is the degree to which it satisfies a specified set of attributes or requirements.
INDICATORS	A description of the project's objectives in terms of quantity, quality, target group(s), time and place.

Annex 1. Work Package 6: Monitoring and evaluation activities (what, how, where) and division of work

Task No (continuous numbering)	Task Name	Description	Participants		In-kind Contributions and Subcontracting (Yes/No and which)
			Name	Role (COO, BEN, AE, AP, OTHER)	

linked to WP)					
T6.1	Quality assurance plan, including key performance indicators (KPIs)	The Quality Assurance Plan, drafted in the initial phases of the project, will serve as a comprehensive guide covering a range of critical aspects to ensure the highest standards of quality across all project activities, namely: 1. Actionable and practical advice for maintaining high-quality standards across all project activities, ensuring that every task is performed with excellence and precision. 2. A set of detailed rules and procedures for both online and offline dissemination activities, according to legal and ethical standards, including guidelines for sharing information and engaging with stakeholders in a manner that respects privacy, intellectual property, and other relevant norms. 3. Robust monitoring and control mechanisms designed to oversee the project's progress effectively and enable timely identification and resolution of issues, ensuring that the project stays on track and meets its objectives. 4. Standardized models and templates for the project's deliverables and reports, facilitating efficient monitoring and evaluation, to provide a consistent format for documentation, making it easier to review progress, assess quality, and ensure that all outputs meet the project's requirements.	CERTH, HU, YET, HELIX ISIM, EITM, IIW, EWF, CTA, REDAS P, CSC, IMPACT, SUDOTIM	COO BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN	20% In-kind support from each partner.
T6.3	Periodic quality reviews	The Quality Assurance Manager (QAM) from IMPACTSCI is tasked with continuous monitoring of all work packages, focusing particularly on the execution processes. From the commencement of the project	CERTH, HU, YET, HELIX ISIM,	COO BEN BEN BEN BEN	20% In-kind support from each partner.

		<p>and following the generation of significant outcomes, the QAM will conduct regular quality assessments (biannually) to ensure they align with the project's predefined goals and characteristics. QAM is accountable to the SC, providing insights from six biannual and three annual quality evaluations. These will contribute to the project's progress reports and play a crucial role in the comprehensive interim and final evaluation reports submitted to EACEA. Quality review reports will be compiled, detailing the activities post-production of the project's main intellectual outputs. Should any deviations from the established high-quality benchmarks be identified, the QAM will notify the Steering Committee and collaborate with the EQAB to pinpoint and implement the necessary corrective measures.</p>	EITM, IIW, EWF, CTA, REDAS P, CSC, IMPAC T , SUDOTI M	BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN	
T6.4	External evaluator selection	<p>The project's managerial boards will establish specific criteria for selecting an external evaluator to ensure the external assessment's quality, transparency, and impartiality. The SC is responsible for approving these selection criteria. The External Evaluator must possess essential skills and qualifications, including relevant evaluation experience and a clear absence of any conflict of interest. CERTH, as the leading partner, alongside IMPACTSCI, will organize and conduct the tender process for the External Evaluator. The call for applications will be advertised on the project and partner websites and disseminated through academic and research networks throughout Europe. The selection process will follow a two-step approach: 1. Interested evaluators will express their interest by submitting their</p>	CERTH , HU, YET, HELIX ISIM, EITM, IIW, EWF, CTA, REDAS P, CSC, IMPAC T , SUDOTI M	COO BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN	N/A

		curriculum vitae (CV), references, and a motivation letter to CERTH. 2. The shortlisted candidates will then be interviewed by representatives from CERTH and members of the Steering Committee.			
T6.5	External evaluation strategy	The chosen external evaluator will compile an exhaustive list of key results and outcomes from each work package, assessing their significance to the project's overall impact. They will pinpoint relevant data sources and establish the schedule for evaluation reports and key timelines. Tools for the evaluation will be selected, including the project's progress reports, deliverables, stakeholder feedback, online surveys, interview frameworks, statistical techniques, and more. This information will be organized into a preliminary Evaluation Blueprint document, which will be shared with all project partners. Following their feedback, the document will be finalized.	External Evaluator CERTH	OTHER COO	N/A
T6.6	External evaluation deployment	The External Evaluator will implement the assessment process based on identified impact factors (results and outcomes influencing impact) and prepare two interim and one final evaluation to be integrated in interim and final reporting to EACEA. The reports will identify risk developments of project implementation and signal the SC, EQAB and the project's internal managerial committees for corrective actions if needed.	External Evaluator CERTH	OTHER COO	N/A
T6.1	Quality assurance plan, including key performance	The Quality Assurance Plan, drafted in the initial phases of the project, will serve as a comprehensive guide covering a range of critical aspects to ensure the highest standards of quality across all project activities, namely: 1. Actionable and practical advice for maintaining high-	CERTH, HU, YET, HELIX ISIM, EITM, IIW,	COO BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN	20% In-kind support from each partner.

	indicators (KPIs)	<p>quality standards across all project activities, ensuring that every task is performed with excellence and precision. 2. A set of detailed rules and procedures for both online and offline dissemination activities, according to legal and ethical standards, including guidelines for sharing information and engaging with stakeholders in a manner that respects privacy, intellectual property, and other relevant norms. 3. Robust monitoring and control mechanisms designed to oversee the project's progress effectively and enable timely identification and resolution of issues, ensuring that the project stays on track and meets its objectives. 4. Standardized models and templates for the project's deliverables and reports, facilitating efficient monitoring and evaluation, to provide a consistent format for documentation, making it easier to review progress, assess quality, and ensure that all outputs meet the project's requirements.</p>	EWF, CTA, REDAS P, CSC, IMPAC T, SUDOTI M	BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN	
T6.3	Periodic quality reviews	<p>The Quality Assurance Manager (QAM) from IMPACTSCI is tasked with continuous monitoring of all work packages, focusing particularly on the execution processes. From the commencement of the project and following the generation of significant outcomes, the QAM will conduct regular quality assessments (biannually) to ensure they align with the project's predefined goals and characteristics. QAM is accountable to the SC, providing insights from six biannual and three annual quality evaluations. These will contribute to the project's progress reports and play a crucial role in the comprehensive interim and final evaluation reports submitted to EACEA.</p>	CERTH, HU, YET, HELIX ISIM, EITM, IIW, EWF, CTA, REDAS P, CSC, IMPAC T, SUDOTI M	COO BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN BEN	20% In-kind support from each partner.

		<p>Quality review reports will be compiled, detailing the activities post-production of the project's main intellectual outputs. Should any deviations from the established high-quality benchmarks be identified, the QAM will notify the Steering Committee and collaborate with the EQAB to pinpoint and implement the necessary corrective measures.</p>			
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Annex 2. The project quality assurance and evaluation specific deliverables (outputs/outcomes).

Deliverable No (continuous numbering linked to WP)	Deliverable Name	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month number)	Description (including format and language)
D6.1	Quality assurance plan	6	HELIX	[R – Document, report]	[PU – Public]	M3	An integrated report (40 pages) containing the Quality assurance plan & indicators. Will be issued in EN, RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT, DE.

D6.2	Internal quality assurance report	6	IMPACT	[R – Document, report]	[PU – Public]	M18 and M36	An integrated quality assurance report issued following the period quality controls of all the declared indicators. One interim report (50 pages) and one updated final report (50 pages) will be issued in English.
D6.3	External evaluation strategy	6	External Evaluator	[R – Document, report]	[PU – Public]	M6	An initial report explaining the external evaluation (at least 50 pages in English).
D6.4	External evaluation report	6	External Evaluator	[R – Document, report]	[PU – Public]	M18 and M36	One interim report (50 pages) and one updated final report

							(50 pages) will be issued in English as part of the external evaluation task.
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Annex 3. Quality assurance and evaluation indicators during the project implementation timeline

Indicator	Base value	Target value	Measurement unit	Measurement method
CMW modules developed and integrated into university curricula (quant)	0	5	Number of modules	Complete learning pack developed
CMW modules developed and integrated into VET curricula (quant)	0	5	Number of modules	Complete learning pack developed
Number of project partners registered as DTTI pledgers	2	14	Number of registered partners	DTTI Pledge confirmation
CMW modules developed and integrated into the DTTI Pledge	0	5	Number of modules	Approval from the DTTI Team
Number of train-the-trainers modules (quant)	0	5	Number of modules	Complete learning pack developed
Number of trained learners on CMW (quant)	0	5000	Number of registrations	Record/log keeping

Number of trained trainers in CMW (quant)	0	250	# of certifications	Record/log keeping
Number of learners from social groups at risk involved in the project (quant) - particularly disabilities (visible and invisible)	0	500	# of certifications	Record/log keeping
Number of learners involved in blended work-based learning secondments (quant)	0	100	Number of registrations	Record/log keeping
Number of companies engaged in the WELDIFY platform (quant)	0	100	Number of registrations	Record/log keeping
Number of universities and VET centres that will uptake the WELDIFY platform (quant)	0	50	Number of companies	Record/log keeping
Number of modernised university and VET related CMW curricula (quant)	0	25	Number of institutions	Record/log keeping
Learner satisfaction with regards to the WELDIFY online platform (quant + qual) - 35% increase from day 1 to end of training	0	> 85% satisfaction with	1-5 scale index	Perceptions survey with regards to learner satisfaction
Make CMW workforce more productive (quant)		20% increase	Productivity metrics	Checking company reports
Learner digital competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant)	after pre-assessment	35% increase	1-5 point scale for DigComp	Self-assessed DigComp survey (pre and post training)

Learner green competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant)	after pre-assessment	30% increase	1-5 point scale for GreenComp	Self-assessed GreenComp survey (pre and post training)
Learner entrepreneurship competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant)	after pre-assessment	35% increase	1-5 point scale for EntreComp	Self-assessed EntreComp survey (pre and post training)
Trainer competence increase with regards to online education delivery (sample of 250 trainers) (quant)	after pre-assessment	25% increase	1-5 point scale for DigCompEdu	Self-assessed DigCompEdu survey (pre and post training)
Number of dropouts from university/VET (quant)	after pre-assessment	25% decrease	Number of learners	Comparing drop-outs in year 1 and in year 3 learners database
Amount of funding obtained to sustain WELDIFY activities (quant)	0	500 000	EUR	Combined budget from new projects required to sustain WELDIFY' efforts
# of policy makers interested to use WELDIFY platform for promoting regional safety, sustainability and industrial resilience (quant)		20	Number of policy makers	Record/log keeping
Number of companies outside of the consortium interested to use WELDIFY platform for upskilling their employees (quant)	0	30	Number of companies	Record/log keeping

Make online education more inclusive (quant + qual)	after pre assessment	45% increase	Subjective/personal reflections	Pre and post assessment (before and after the trainings)
Degree of learners feeling empowered to be in charge of their own learning path (quant + qual)	TBD after pre assessment	30% increase	Subjective/personal reflections on key indicators	Pre and post assessment (before and after the trainings)
Increase of employability	Statistical average	15-30% increase in 6-12 months	Percentage	Comparing yearly statistics
Overall satisfaction level of the involved project team (quant + qual)	0	>85%	Subjective reflections	Post assessment at the project completion
Social media engagements / reactions (quant)		100000	# of reaction	Social media metrics
Website visitors (quant)	0	5000	# of visitors	Google analytics
Implementation conformance (quant)	0	<10% change	Percentage	Measuring timeline changes

Deep-tech driven inclusive and socially-aware circular material joining & welding for a safe future

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